

Functional Outcomes of Anterior & Posterolateral Rotatory Instability of Knee Managed with Arthroscopic ACL Reconstruction and Modified Larson Technique

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Abstract

Background: Most common cause of failure following ACL reconstruction surgery is missing of posterolateral corner injuries. Posterolateral corner injuries are one of the most debilitating conditions that affects the knee joint, usually not occurring in isolation. It is frequently underdiagnosed (or) undertreated, resulting in the poor outcome of the ACL reconstruction surgeries performed. Through this paper it is firmly established that repairing the structures in the posterolateral corner using the modified Larson technique significantly improves the overall functional outcome of the patient and overall performance. Most of the patients presenting with PLC injuries will have reported instability affecting the daily activities of the person.

Aim: To assess the functional outcome arthroscopic ACL reconstruction AND Modified Larson technique reconstruction done together.

Settings and Design: Last 5 years retrospective review of functional outcome of both Arthroscopic ACLR and modified Larson technique reconstruction done together.

Methods: 20 patients retrospective review with Lysholm-Tegner and IKDC (subjective).

Results: Excellent to good functional outcome. 18 person showed excellent functional outcome and 2 person showed good functional outcome.

Conclusions: ACL along with posterolateral corner injuries where the popliteus is not injured adding modified Larson technique to arthroscopic ACLR is of immense value.

Keywords: ACLR and modified larsen technique.

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Introduction

Posterolateral corner instability occurs mostly in association with cruciate ligament injury with only 28% occurring in isolation. Posterolateral corner injuries are mostly missed by the beginners who don't look and examine the posterolateral corner for injuries at the knee [1]. So it is essential to look for Posterolateral corner injuries in each and every knee injury patient presenting with instability. Posterolateral corner once referred to as the dark side of the knee because of the limitations in understanding of our

anatomy, biomechanics and functional significance rarely heals non operatively. Advancements in the understanding of anatomy, biomechanics have led to development of techniques that address this unexplored area of ligament instability. Here, we made a systematic approach to diagnose and improve the function outcomes of such patients with Arthroscopic ACL reconstruction and modified Larson technique reconstruction done together. [2]

Table 1: Modified Hughston classification

Grade	Examination	Findings
Grade 1	0-5mm of lateral opening on varus stress test 0-5 degree rotational instability on dial test	Sprain, no tensile failure of capsuloligamentous structures
Grade 2	6-10mm of lateral opening on varus stress test 6-10 degree rotational instability on dial test	Partial injuries with moderate ligament disruption
Grade 3	>10mm of lateral opening on varus stress test no end point > 10 degree rotational instability on dial test	Complete ligament disruption

Source: Hughston JC, Jacobson KE. Chronic posterolateral instability of the knee. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1985; 67:351–359.

Figure 1: Pre-Op Evaluation Showing Positive Dial Test

Figure 2: Preop Xrays Showing Increased Joint Space (More Than 4mm On Varus Stress Compared To Normal Side)

Figure 3: MRI Showing the ACL And PLC Injury

Figure 4: Immediate Post Operative Xrays

Figure 5: Follow Up At 3 Year

Methods and Materials:

From 2017 to 2022 patients with knee instability were clinically assessed and those suspected for ACL and posterolateral corner injuries were identified following which varus stress X rays were take and categorised according to the modified Hutchinson classification. MRI taken to rule out other ligament injuries. Informed consent obtained. About 20 patients with grade 3 injury were selected. Reop rehabilitation was advised for all the

patients. Combined ACL reconstruction and modified Larson technique done as a single step procedure in our institute. Patients, where discharged at 14 days post operatively with strict adherence to post operative rehabilitation protocol.

All the 20 patients came for follow up. They were analysed for the functional outcome using knee scores as Tegner score, IKDC subjective score at regular intervals. A minimum follows up of 3yrs is

maintained with patient reviewed in 1,2,3,6,12,18,24,36 months

Results:

Strict objective score was used for the evaluation of functional outcome. All the

patients showed significant improvement in their functional outcome. Total 18 person showed excellent functional outcome and 2 person showed good functional outcome.

Table 2: Gender Based Functional Outcome

Gender	Number of person	Preop Tegner score	Postop Tegner score
Male	17	45	>90
	2		86
Female	1	40	>90

Table 3: Lifestyle Based Functional Outcome

Lifestyle	Number of person	Pre-Op IKDC score	Post-Op IKDC score
Athletic	2	20	95
Moderate activity	12	25	94
	2	25	86
Sedenary lifestyle	4	30	94

Discussion

Our study is one where long term follow up of the patients over 3 years is followed resulting in establishing long term results of this combined operative technique. [3]

The initial mechanism of injury of posterolateral rotatory instability do not produce any immediate functional restriction but over the next few years this results in very debilitating condition of the knee. This technique aims at the reconstruction of fibular collateral ligament and popliteo fibular ligament along with reconstruction of anterior cruciate ligament. [4]

The major advantage of modified Larson technique is the relative straight forward nature of this technique for reconstruction of posterolateral corner structures. This technique is less invasive and less technically demanding than other methods of anatomical reconstruction. [5]

The major setback of modified Larson technique is that this technique does not involve reconstruction of popliteus tendon which when injured may provide additional reinforcement on repair. Various authorities have recommended the combined reconstruction of ACL and

posterolateral corner injury yield less stress on the ACL graft that the solitary cruciate ligament reconstruction thereby preventing graft failure. [6]

The post operative functional assessment for these patients revealed an excellent functional outcome with an excellent Tegner-Lysholm score and IKDC score. Various medical literature all point that repairing the posterolateral corner using modified Larson technique provides significant improvement in the patient's future outcome.

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